

Vitamin- D Supplementation with Moderate Exercise Enhance Plasma Insulin Levels in Prediabetes and Type 2 Diabetes Patients

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to investigate the relationship between the supplementation of vitamin -D with moderate exercise (ME) on plasma insulin level in Indian subjects of Pre and Type 2 diabetes mellitus. Several observational studies suggest that vitamin-D plays a role in the pathogenesis of pre and Type2 diabetes. We investigate the effect of ME with Vitamin-D supplementation in the pathogenesis of diabetes.

Method: The Plasma Insulin and vitamin- D levels were measured using Radioimmunoassay and ELISA. We measured plasma Insulin level in the Indian subjects of age group (30-50 years) of N30, before and after vitamin- D supplementation with ME for the following groups. Vitamin- D deficient with Pre diabetes mellitus (PDM), vitamin -D deficient with Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), vitamin- D deficient with non-diabetes mellitus (NDM) and ME alone.

Result: We observed that, plasma Insulin level were significantly ($P<0.05$) increased after supplementation of vitamin- D with moderate exercise when compare to and ME alone.

Conclusion: This study suggests that Vitamin- D supplementation with moderate exercise may improve insulin secretion from β cells in Vitamin -D deficient with PDM and T2DM cases.

Keywords: Vitamin-D, Pre diabetes, Insulin, Type 2 diabetes.

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Introduction

The rapid increase in prevalence of diabetes has become a major distress for India and the World. The initial Pre diabetes is prevalent in the global population progression to diabetes can occur because of worsening insulin resistance, Pancreatic

β -cell dysfunction or both. In case without intervention, Pre diabetes is likely to become Type-2 diabetes, with in short period[1]. The β -cell dysfunction is an important contributor to the pathogenesis of type 2 diabetes[2,3].

Rickets and osteomalacia can be prevented and treated with vitamin D, which is essential for bone and mineral metabolism[4-8]. There have been many studies on possible extra-skeletal effects of vitamin D due to the fact that vitamin D receptors (VDRs) are expressed in practically every tissue and cell[9-17]. Epidemiological research has demonstrated a strong interest in vitamin D due to the association between low 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25[OH]D) concentrations and a number of acute and chronic illnesses[18,19].

Several observational studies have related vitamin D deficiency (VDD) to Type-2 diabetes[20] and metabolic syndrome[21]. Advantageous effects of vitamin D have been demonstrated on both insulin sensitivity and β -cell function in several animal model studies[22-24]. Furthermore, other studies have suggested an interesting involvement of vitamin D in the impairment β -cell secretion[25-26]. 2010. However, published clinical trials shows supplementation of Vit D in subjects with Type-2-diabetes and Prediabetes have inconsistent results[27]. A greater improvement in the insulin sensitivity [28] and metabolic syndrome after exercise[29-30]. was reported. However, in some cases Type- 2 diabetes and Pre diabetes single exposure of Vit D or ME alone could not show significant effect for this reason and based on earlier studies we hypothesized that combine effect of VitD supplementation along with moderate exercise assign potential effect on β -cell function. Further, no previous study has examined the combine effect of (ME+ Vit D) on insulin secretion in Vitamin D deficient diabetes patients. Hence, this study has been undertaken.

There is general agreement that providing toddlers and newborns with 400 IU of vitamin D daily can prevent nutritional rickets[31]. More debatable are the possible extra-skeletal effects of vitamin D and the skeletal effects of vitamin D insufficiency

in adults and older individuals (aged >65 years). Some people believe that taking vitamin D supplements is pointless[32]. Others, however, have argued that people should strive to reach 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25OHD) concentrations comparable to those found in some tribes in equatorial Africa with a sun exposure lifestyle that may be similar to that of early humans[33-37]. This is because the vitamin D intake requirement is much higher than what the general population currently achieves.

Vitamin D supplementation only demonstrated a non-significant trend to delay the progression of prediabetes into T2DM in the large D2d RCT of individuals with prediabetes. People who got vitamin D (4,000 IU per day) and had a high risk of developing T2DM were purposefully included in the trial. In the ITT analysis, the vitamin D group's hazard ratio for developing T2DM was 0.88 (95% CI 0.75-1.04; P = 0.12) higher than that of the placebo group. However, in a post hoc analysis, those with a baseline BMI under 30 mg/m², severe vitamin D deficiency at baseline, complete adherence to medication throughout the study, or blood 25OHD above 100 nmol/l during the study[38] showed a significant benefit.

Materials and method:

The outpatients and inpatients were collected from the Nandha Medical College and Hospital Erode, Tamilnadu. Prior written and informed consent was obtained from every patient and the study was approved by the Intuitional ethical committee. The subjects were divided into four groups. Vitamin- D deficient with Pre diabetes mellitus (PDM), vitamin - D deficient with Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), vitamin- D deficient with non-diabetes mellitus (NDM) and Mild exercise (ME) alone. Abnormal BMI patients were excluded. Moderate exercise (ME): Mild walking morning 1 hr daily Vitamin D supplementation given 5000 IU per day given.

Blood samples were collected and the Plasma Insulin and vitamin- D levels were measured in control and experimental group using Radioimmunoassay and ELISA

Results

In this study before and after supplementation of vit D or moderate exercise or both, the vitamin D and

insulin level were analyzed. We observed that, plasma Insulin level were significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased after supplementation of vitamin- D with moderate exercise in Vitamin- D deficient with Prediabetes mellitus (PDM), vitamin-D deficient with Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), vitamin- D deficient with non-diabetes mellitus (NDM) which is shown in figure 1-7. One way ANOVA used to analyze the data.

Figure 1: Vitamin- D deficient with non-diabetes mellitus (NDM) Supplement Vit D+ME (Moderate Exercise) Result: mean \pm SEM (n=30), significant($P < 0.05$)

Figure 2: Vitamin-D deficient with Prediabetes mellitus (PDM) supplement Moderate exercise (ME) alone Result: mean \pm SEM (n=30), non-significant

Figure 3: Vitamin- D deficient with Prediabetes mellitus (PDM) Supplement Vit D alone Result: mean \pm SEM (n=30), non-significant

Figure 4: Vitamin- D deficient with Prediabetes mellitus (PDM) Supplement Vit D+ME (Moderate exercise) Result: mean \pm SEM (n=30), significant($P < 0.05$)

In this study after supplementation of Vit D with moderate exercise significantly increases the plasma insulin level. Similarly earlier studies reported that after aerobic training (AT) and resistance training (RT) significantly larger improvements in beta cell function in overweight adults[39] and in mice[40].

Figure 5: Vitamin -D deficient with Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) Supplement ME (Moderate exercise) Result: mean \pm SEM (n=30), non-significant

However, the exact mechanisms of vitamin D effect on insulin secretion in the presence of glucose are not yet fully understood and need further studies, but it has been reported that vitamin D directly increases insulin secretion in beta cells[42]. The mechanism may occur due to the presence of vitamin D receptors (VDR) on pancreatic β cells in the islets of Langerhans [30]. Faure et al. have reported that vitamin D enhances Ca^{2+} entry or Ca^{2+} mobilization in β cells, which could indirectly amplify insulin secretion[43]. In addition current research supports a direct effect of vitamin D on insulin formation and release because due to the presence of the vitamin D response element in the human

Vitamin D supplementation increases the beta cell insulin secretion in animal and human models[41]. However compare to pervious study in this study we observed that combined effect of supplementation Vita D with ME shows better performance of beta cell - insulin secretion compare to single exposure Vit D or ME alone.

Fig 6: Vitamin -D deficient with Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) Supplement Vit D alone Result: mean \pm SEM (n=30), non-significant

insulin gene promoter and the transcriptional activity of the human insulin gene caused by 1, 25-dihydroxyvitamin D (the active form of vitamin D)[44-45].

Huang HH et al have reported exercise has an effect on the pancreatic islets by stimulating insulin production and/or secretion in diabetic animals[40]. Conversely, exercise on β -cell health indicate exercise partially spared the β -cells from diabetes. However, the exact mechanisms of exercise effect on insulin secretion in beta cell not yet fully understood and need further studies

Conclusion

This study concludes that in Vitamin D deficient diabetes cases vitamin D supplementation not only sufficient to enhance the insulin secretion the is a moderate exercise also required with the supplementation of Vit D

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Institutional Ethical Committee approval:

Nandha Medical College and Hospital, Erode College's intuitional Ethical Committee assessed and approved the survey project. Informed consent obtained from all the participants.

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All authors approved the final manuscript as submitted and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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